

VIKOR Based MAGDM strategy under Bipolar Neutrosophic Set Environment

Surapati Pramanik¹, Shyamal Dalapati², Shariful Alam³, Tapan Kumar Roy⁴,

¹ Department of Mathematics, Nandalal Ghosh B.T. College, Panpur, P.O.-Narayanpur, District –North 24 Parganas, Pin code-743126, West Bengal, India. E-mail: sura_pati@yahoo.co.in

² Department of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur, P.O.-Botanic Garden, Howrah-711103, West Bengal, India. E-mail: dalapatishyamal30@gmail.com

³ Department of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur, P.O.-Botanic Garden, Howrah-711103, West Bengal, India. E-mail: salam50in@yahoo.co.in

⁴Department of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur, West Bengal, India

Abstract. In this paper, we extend the VIKOR (VIsekriterijumska optimizacija i KOmpromisno Resenje) strategy to multiple attribute group decision-making (MAGDM) with bipolar neutrosophic set environment. In this paper, we first define VIKOR strategy in bipolar neutrosophic set environment to handle MAGDM problems, which means we combine the VIKOR with bipolar neutrosophic number to deal with MAGDM. We

propose a new strategy for solving MAGDM. Finally, we solve MAGDM problem using our newly proposed VIKOR strategy under bipolar neutrosophic set environment. Further, we present sensitivity analysis to show the impact of different values of the decision making mechanism coefficient on ranking order of the alternatives.

Keywords: Bipolar neutrosophic sets, VIKOR strategy, Multi attribute group decision making.

1 Introduction

In 1965, Zadeh [1] first introduced the fuzzy set to deal with the vague, imprecise data in real life specifying the membership degree of an element. Thereafter, in 1986 Atanassov [2] introduced intuitionistic fuzzy set to tackle the uncertainty in data in real life expressing membership degree and non-membership degree of an element as independent component. As a generalization of classical set, fuzzy set and intuitionistic fuzzy set, Smarandache [3] introduced the neutrosophic set by expressing the membership degree (truth membership degree), indeterminacy degree and non-membership degree (falsity membership degree) of an element independently. For real applications of neutrosophic set, Wang et al. [4] introduced the single valued neutrosophic set which is a sub class of neutrosophic set.

Decision making process involves selecting the best alternative from the set of feasible alternatives. There exist many decision making strategies in crisp set environment [5-7], fuzzy [8-12], intuitionistic fuzzy set environment [13-19], vague set environment [20, 21]. Theoretical as well as practical applications multi attribute decision making (MADM) of SVNS environment [22-42] and interval neutrosophic set (INS) environment [43-56] have been reported in the literature. Recently, decision

making in hybrid neutrosophic set environment have drawn much attention of the researches such as rough neutrosophic environment [57-73], neutrosophic soft set environment [74-80], neutrosophic soft expert set environment [81-82], neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy set environment [83-87], neutrosophic refined set environment [88-93], neutrosophic cubic set environment [94-104], etc. In 2015, Deli *et al.* [105] proposed bipolar neutrosophic set (BNS) using the concept of bipolar fuzzy sets [106, 107] and neutrosophic sets [3]. A BNS consists of two fully independent parts, which are positive membership degrees $T^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $I^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $F^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and negative membership degrees $T^- \rightarrow [-1, 0]$, $I^- \rightarrow [-1, 0]$, $F^- \rightarrow [-1, 0]$ where the positive membership degrees T^+ , I^+ , F^+ represent truth membership degree, indeterminacy membership degree and false membership degree respectively of an element and the negative membership degrees T^- , I^- , F^- represent truth membership degree, indeterminacy membership degree and false membership degree respectively of an element to some implicit counter property corresponding to a BNS. Deli *et al.* [105] defined some operations namely, score function, accuracy function, and certainty function to compare BNSs and provided some operators in order to aggregate BNSs. Deli and Subas [108] defined correlation coefficient similarity measure for dealing with MADM problems under bipolar set

environment. Şahin *et al.* [109] proposed Jaccard vector similarity measure for MADM problems under bipolar neutrosophic set environment. Uluçay *et al.* [110] presented Dice similarity measure, weighted Dice similarity measure, hybrid vector similarity measure, weighted hybrid vector similarity measure for BNSs and established a MADM strategy by employing the proposed similarity measures. Dey *et al.* [111] established TOPSIS strategy for MADM problems with bipolar neutrosophic information where the weights of the attributes are completely unknown to the decision maker. Pramanik *et al.* [112] defined projection, bidirectional projection and hybrid projection measures for BNSs and proved their basic properties. In the same study, Pramanik *et al.* [112], proposed three new MADM strategies based on the proposed projection, bidirectional projection and hybrid projection measures with bipolar neutrosophic information. Wang *et al.* [113] defined Frank operations of bipolar neutrosophic numbers (BNNs) and proposed Frank bipolar neutrosophic Choquet Bonferroni mean operators by combining Choquet integral operators and Bonferroni mean operators based on Frank operations of BNNs. In the same study, Wang *et al.* [113] developed MADM strategy based on Frank Choquet Bonferroni operators of BNNs in bipolar neutrosophic environment. Recently, many researcher has given attention to develop various strategies under bipolar neutrosophic set environment in various fields [114-117].

Opricovic [118] proposed the VIKOR strategy for a MCDM problem with conflicting attributes [119-120]. In 2015, Bausys and Zavadskas [121] proposed VIKOR strategy to solve multi criteria decision making problem in interval neutrosophic set environment. Further, Hung *et al.* [122] proposed VIKOR strategy for interval neutrosophic multi attribute group decision making (MAGDM). Poursmaeil *et al.* [123] proposed a MAGDM strategy based on TOPSIS and VIKOR strategies in single valued neutrosophic set environment. Liu and Zhang [124] extended VIKOR strategy in neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy set environment. Hu *et al.* [125] proposed interval neutrosophic projection based VIKOR strategy and applied it for doctor selection. Selvakumari *et al.* [126] proposed VIKOR strategy for decision making problem using octagonal neutrosophic soft matrix.

VIKOR strategy in bipolar neutrosophic set is yet to appear.

Research gap:

VIKOR based MAGDM strategy in BNS environment. This study answers the following research questions:

- i. Is it possible to extend VIKOR strategy in BNS environment?

- ii. Is it possible to develop a new VIKOR based MAGDM strategy in BNS environment?

Motivation:

The above-mentioned analysis [118-126] describes the motivation behind proposing a novel VIKOR strategy for MAGDM in the BNS environment. This study develops a novel VIKOR strategy for MAGDM that can deal with multiple decision-makers.

The objectives of the paper are:

- i. To extend VIKOR strategy in BNS environment.
- ii. To develop a new MAGDM strategy based on proposed VIKOR strategy in BNS environment.

To fill the research gap, we propose VIKOR based strategy, which is capable of dealing with MAGDM problem in BNS environment.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized below:

- i. We extend VIKOR strategy in bipolar neutrosophic environment.
- ii. We introduce a bipolar neutrosophic weighted aggregation operator and prove its basic properties.
- iii. We develop a novel VIKOR based MAGDM strategy in bipolar neutrosophic set environment to solve MAGDM problems.
- iv. In this paper, we solve a MAGDM problem based on proposed VIKOR strategy.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In the Section 2, we review some basic concepts and operations related to neutrosophic set, single valued neutrosophic set (SVNS), bipolar neutrosophic set. In Section 3, we propose the bipolar neutrosophic number weighted aggregation (BNNWA) operator and prove its basic properties. In section 4, we develop a novel MAGDM strategy based on VIKOR strategy to solve the MAGDM problems with bipolar neutrosophic information. In Section 5, we present an example to illustrate the proposed strategy. Then in Section 6, we present the sensitivity analysis to show the impact of different values of the decision making mechanism coefficient on ranking order of the alternatives. In section 7, we present conclusion and future direction of research.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we describe the basic definitions related to neutrosophic sets, bipolar neutrosophic sets.

Definition 2.1 Neutrosophic set

Let U be a space of points (objects), with a generic element in U denoted by u . A neutrosophic sets [3] A in U is characterized by a truth-membership function $T_A(u)$, an

indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(u)$ and a falsity-membership function $F_A(u)$,

where, $T_A(u), I_A(u), F_A(u) : U \rightarrow]^-0, 1^+[$.

Neutrosophic set A can be written as:

$$A = \{ u, \langle T_A(u), I_A(u), F_A(u) \rangle : u \in U \},$$

where, $T_A(u), I_A(u), F_A(u) \in]^-0, 1^+[$.

The sum of $T_A(u), I_A(u), F_A(u)$ is

$$^-0 \leq T_A(u) + I_A(u) + F_A(u) \leq 3^+.$$

Definition 2.2: Single valued neutrosophic set

Let U be a space of points (objects) with a generic element in U denoted by u. A single valued neutrosophic set [4] J in U is characterized by a truth-membership function $T_J(u)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_J(u)$ and a falsity-membership function $F_J(u)$, where,

$$T_J(u), I_J(u), F_J(u) : U \rightarrow]0, 1].$$

A single valued neutrosophic set J can be expressed by

$$J = \{ u, \langle T_J(u), I_J(u), F_J(u) \rangle : u \in U \}.$$

Therefore for each $u \in U$, $T_J(u), I_J(u), F_J(u) \in]0, 1]$ the sum of three functions lies between 0 and 1, i.e.

$$0 \leq T_J(u) + I_J(u) + F_J(u) \leq 3.$$

Definition 2.3: Bipolar neutrosophic set

Let U be a space of points (objects) with a generic element in U denoted by u. A bipolar neutrosophic set [105] H in U is defined as an object of the form

$$H = \{ u, \langle T_H^+(u), I_H^+(u), F_H^+(u), T_H^-(u), I_H^-(u), F_H^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \},$$

where,

$$T_H^+(u), I_H^+(u), F_H^+(u) : U \rightarrow]0, 1]$$

and

$$T_H^-(u), I_H^-(u), F_H^-(u) : U \rightarrow]-1, 0].$$

We denote

$$H = \{ u, \langle T_H^+(u), I_H^+(u), F_H^+(u), T_H^-(u), I_H^-(u), F_H^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$$

imply $H = \langle T_H^+, I_H^+, F_H^+, T_H^-, I_H^-, F_H^- \rangle$ as a bipolar neutrosophic number (BNN).

Definition 2.4 Containment of two bipolar neutrosophic sets [105]

Let

$$H_1 = \{ u, \langle T_1^+(u), I_1^+(u), F_1^+(u), T_1^-(u), I_1^-(u), F_1^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$$

and

$$H_2 = \{ u, \langle T_2^+(u), I_2^+(u), F_2^+(u), T_2^-(u), I_2^-(u), F_2^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$$

be any two bipolar neutrosophic sets in U. Then $H_1 \subseteq H_2$ iff

$$T_1^+(u) \leq T_2^+(u), \quad I_1^+(u) \geq I_2^+(u), \quad F_1^+(u) \geq F_2^+(u)$$

and

$$T_1^-(u) \geq T_2^-(u), \quad I_1^-(u) \leq I_2^-(u), \quad F_1^-(u) \leq F_2^-(u)$$

for all $u \in U$.

Definition 2.5 Equality of two bipolar neutrosophic sets [103]

Let

$$H_1 = \{ u, \langle T_1^+(u), I_1^+(u), F_1^+(u), T_1^-(u), I_1^-(u), F_1^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$$

and

$$H_2 = \{ u, \langle T_2^+(u), I_2^+(u), F_2^+(u), T_2^-(u), I_2^-(u), F_2^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$$

be any two bipolar neutrosophic sets in U. Then,

$$H_1 = H_2 \text{ iff } \quad T_1^+(u) = T_2^+(u), \quad I_1^+(u) = I_2^+(u),$$

$$F_1^+(u) = F_2^+(u) \text{ and } \quad T_1^-(u) = T_2^-(u), \quad I_1^-(u) = I_2^-(u),$$

$$F_1^-(u) = F_2^-(u) \text{ for all } u \in U.$$

Definition 2.6 Union of any two bipolar neutrosophic sets [105]

Let $H_1 = \{ u, \langle T_1^+(u), I_1^+(u), F_1^+(u), T_1^-(u), I_1^-(u), F_1^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$ and $H_2 = \{ u, \langle T_2^+(u), I_2^+(u), F_2^+(u), T_2^-(u), I_2^-(u), F_2^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$ be any two bipolar neutrosophic sets in U. Then, their union is defined as follows:

$$H_3(u) = H_1(u) \cup H_2(u) = \{ u, \langle \max(T_1^+(u), T_2^+(u)), \min(I_1^+(u), I_2^+(u)), \min(F_1^+(u), F_2^+(u)), \min(T_1^-(u), T_2^-(u)), \max(I_1^-(u), I_2^-(u)), \max(F_1^-(u), F_2^-(u)) \rangle : u \in U \}.$$

Definition 2.7 Intersection of two bipolar neutrosophic sets

Let $H_1 = \{ u, \langle T_1^+(u), I_1^+(u), F_1^+(u), T_1^-(u), I_1^-(u), F_1^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$ and $H_2 = \{ u, \langle T_2^+(u), I_2^+(u), F_2^+(u), T_2^-(u), I_2^-(u), F_2^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$ be any two bipolar neutrosophic sets in U. Then, their intersection [105] is defined as follows:

$$H_4(u) = H_1(u) \cap H_2(u) = \{ u, \langle \min(T_1^+(u), T_2^+(u)), \max(I_1^+(u), I_2^+(u)), \max(F_1^+(u), F_2^+(u)), \max(T_1^-(u), T_2^-(u)), \min(I_1^-(u), I_2^-(u)), \min(F_1^-(u), F_2^-(u)) \rangle : u \in U \}$$

for all $u \in U$.

Definition 2.8 Complement of a bipolar neutrosophic set [105]

Let $H_1 = \{ u, \langle T_1^+(u), I_1^+(u), F_1^+(u), T_1^-(u), I_1^-(u), F_1^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$ be a bipolar neutrosophic set in U. Then the complement of H_1 is denoted by H_1^c and is defined by

$$H_1^c = \{ u, \langle 1 - T_1^+(u), 1 - I_1^+(u), 1 - F_1^+(u), \{-1\} - T_1^-(u), \{-1\} - I_1^-(u), \{-1\} - F_1^-(u) \rangle : u \in U \}$$

for all $u \in U$.

Definition 2.13 Hamming distance measure between two BNNs [115]

$$\text{Let } h_1 = \langle T_1^+, I_1^+, F_1^+, T_1^-, I_1^-, F_1^- \rangle \text{ and}$$

$h_2 = \langle T_2^+, I_2^+, F_2^+, T_2^-, I_2^-, F_2^- \rangle$ be any two BNNs in U. Then Hamming distance measure between h_1 and h_2 is

denoted by $D(h_1, h_2)$ and defined as follows:

$$D(h_1, h_2) = \frac{1}{6} [|T_1^+ - T_2^+| + |I_1^+ - I_2^+| + |F_1^+ - F_2^+| + |T_1^- - T_2^-| + |I_1^- - I_2^-| + |F_1^- - F_2^-|] \quad (1)$$

Definition 2.14: Normalization procedure

In decision making situation, cost type attribute and benefit type attribute may exist simultaneously. Assume that, h_{ij} be a BNN to express the rating value of i -th alternative with respect to j -th attribute (c_j). If c_j belongs to the cost type attributes, then h_{ij} should be standardized by employing the complement of BNN h_{ij} . When the attribute c_j belongs to benefit type attributes, h_{ij} does not need to be standardized, we use the following formula of normalization as follows:

$$h_{ij}^* = \langle \{1\} - T_{ij}^+, \{1\} - I_{ij}^+, \{1\} - F_{ij}^+, \{-1\} - T_{ij}^-, \{-1\} - I_{ij}^-, \{-1\} - F_{ij}^- \rangle \quad (2)$$

3. Bipolar neutrosophic number weighted aggregation operator

Let $\{h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t\}$ be the set of t bipolar neutrosophic numbers and $\{\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_t\}$ be the set of corresponding weights of t bipolar neutrosophic numbers with conditions $\beta_p \geq 0$ and $\sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p = 1$. Then the bipolar neutrosophic number weighted aggregation (BNNWA) operator is defined as follows:

$$h_{ij} = \text{BNNWA}_\beta (\tilde{h}_{ij}^1, \tilde{h}_{ij}^2, \dots, \tilde{h}_{ij}^t) = (\beta_1 \tilde{h}_{ij}^1 \oplus \beta_2 \tilde{h}_{ij}^2 \oplus \beta_3 \tilde{h}_{ij}^3 \oplus \dots \oplus \beta_t \tilde{h}_{ij}^t) = \langle \left(\sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p \tilde{T}_{ij}^{+(p)}, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p \tilde{I}_{ij}^{+(p)}, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p \tilde{F}_{ij}^{+(p)}, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p \tilde{T}_{ij}^{-(p)}, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p \tilde{I}_{ij}^{-(p)}, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p \tilde{F}_{ij}^{-(p)} \right) \rangle \quad (3)$$

The BNNWA operator satisfies the following properties:

1. Idempotency
2. Monotonicity
3. Boundedness

Property: 1. Idempotency

If all $h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t = h$ are equal, then

$$h_{ij} = \text{BNNWA}_\beta (h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) = h$$

Proof:

Since $h_{ij}^1 = h_{ij}^2 = \dots = h_{ij}^t = h$, based on the Equation (3)

and with conditions, $\beta_p \geq 0$ and $\sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p = 1$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} h_{ij} &= \text{BNNWA}_\beta (h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) = \\ &(\beta_1 h_{ij}^1 \oplus \beta_2 h_{ij}^2 \oplus \beta_3 h_{ij}^3 \oplus \dots \oplus \beta_t h_{ij}^t) = \\ &(\beta_1 h \oplus \beta_2 h \oplus \beta_3 h \oplus \dots \oplus \beta_t h) = \\ &\langle \left(\sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p T_p^+, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p I_p^+, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p F_p^+, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p T_p^-, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p I_p^-, \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p F_p^- \right) \rangle \\ &= \langle (T^+, I^+, F^+, T^-, I^-, F^-) \rangle = h. \end{aligned}$$

Property: 3. Monotonicity

Assume that $\{h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t\}$ and $\{h_{ij}^{*1}, h_{ij}^{*2}, \dots, h_{ij}^{*t}\}$ be any two set of collections of t bipolar neutrosophic nubers with the condition $t_p^j \leq t_p^{*j}$ ($p = 1, 2, \dots, t$), then

$$\text{BNNWA}_\beta (h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) \leq \text{BNNWA}_\beta (h_{ij}^{*1}, h_{ij}^{*2}, \dots, h_{ij}^{*t}).$$

Proof:

From the given condition $T_{ij}^{+(p)} \leq T_{ij}^{*+(p)}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_p T_{ij}^{+(p)} &\leq \beta_p T_{ij}^{*+(p)} \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p T_{ij}^{+(p)} &\leq \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p T_{ij}^{*+(p)}. \end{aligned}$$

From the given condition $I_{ij}^{+(p)} \geq I_{ij}^{*+(p)}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_p I_{ij}^{+(p)} &\geq \beta_p I_{ij}^{*+(p)} \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p I_{ij}^{+(p)} &\geq \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p I_{ij}^{*+(p)}. \end{aligned}$$

From the given condition $F_{ij}^{+(p)} \geq F_{ij}^{*+(p)}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_p F_{ij}^{+(p)} &\geq \beta_p F_{ij}^{*+(p)} \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p F_{ij}^{+(p)} &\geq \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p F_{ij}^{*+(p)}. \end{aligned}$$

From the given condition $T_{ij}^{-(p)} \geq T_{ij}^{*-(p)}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_p T_{ij}^{-(p)} &\geq \beta_p T_{ij}^{*-(p)} \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p T_{ij}^{-(p)} &\geq \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p T_{ij}^{*-(p)}. \end{aligned}$$

From the given condition $I_{ij}^{-(p)} \leq I_{ij}^{*-(p)}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_p I_{ij}^{-(p)} &\leq \beta_p I_{ij}^{*-(p)} \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p I_{ij}^{-(p)} &\leq \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p I_{ij}^{*-(p)}. \end{aligned}$$

From the given condition $F_{ij}^{-(p)} \leq F_{ij}^{*-(p)}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_p F_{ij}^{-(p)} &\leq \beta_p F_{ij}^{*-(p)} \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p F_{ij}^{-(p)} &\leq \sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p F_{ij}^{*-(p)}. \end{aligned}$$

From the above relations, we obtain

$$\text{BNNWA}_\beta (h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) \leq \text{BNNWA}_\beta (h_{ij}^{*1}, h_{ij}^{*2}, \dots, h_{ij}^{*t}).$$

$$NCNWA_{\beta}(h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) \leq BNNWA_{\beta}(h_{ij}^{*1}, h_{ij}^{*2}, \dots, h_{ij}^{*t}).$$

Property: 2. Boundedness

Let $\{h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t\}$ be any collection of t bipolar neutrosophic numbers.

If

$$h^+ = \langle \max_p \{T_{ij}^{+(p)}\}, \min_p \{I_{ij}^{+(p)}\}, \min_p \{F_{ij}^{+(p)}\}, \min_p \{T_{ij}^{-(p)}\},$$

$$\max_p \{I_{ij}^{-(p)}\}, \max_p \{F_{ij}^{-(p)}\} \rangle$$

$$h^- = \langle \min_p \{T_{ij}^{+(p)}\}, \max_p \{I_{ij}^{+(p)}\}, \max_p \{F_{ij}^{+(p)}\}, \max_p \{T_{ij}^{-(p)}\},$$

$$\min_p \{I_{ij}^{-(p)}\}, \min_p \{F_{ij}^{-(p)}\} \rangle \quad (p=1, 2, 3, \dots, t).$$

Then, $h^- \leq BNNWA_{\beta}(h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) \leq h^+$.

Proof:

From Property 1 and Property 2, we obtain

$$BNNWA_{\beta}(h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) \geq BNNWA_{\beta}(h^-, h^-, \dots, h^-) = h^-$$

and

$$BNNWA_{\beta}(h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) \leq BNNWA_{\beta}(h^+, h^+, \dots, h^+) = h^+.$$

So, we have

$$h^- \leq BNNWA_{\beta}(h_{ij}^1, h_{ij}^2, \dots, h_{ij}^t) \leq h^+.$$

4. VIKOR strategy for solving MAGDM problem under bipolar neutrosophic environment

In this section, we propose a MAGDM strategy under bipolar neutrosophic set environment. Assume that,

$A = \{A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots, A_r\}$ be a set of r alternatives and

$C = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots, c_s\}$ be a set of s attributes. Assume that,

$\alpha = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_s\}$ be the weight vector of the

attributes, where $\alpha_k \geq 0$ and $\sum_{k=1}^s \alpha_k = 1$. Let

$DM = \{DM_1, DM_2, DM_3, \dots, DM_t\}$ be the set of t decision makers and $\beta = \{\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_t\}$ be the set of weight vector

of decision makers, where $\beta_p \geq 0$ and $\sum_{p=1}^t \beta_p = 1$.

In this section, we describe the VIKOR based MAGDM strategy under bipolar neutrosophic set environment. The proposed strategy consists of the following steps (see Figure 1):

Step: 1. Construction of the decision matrix

Let $M^p = (h_{ij}^p)_{r \times s}$ ($p = 1, 2, 3, \dots, t$) be the p-th decision matrix, where information about the alternative A_i is provided by the decision maker DM_p with respect to attribute C_j ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$). The p-th decision matrix denoted by M^p (See eq. (4)) is constructed as follows:

$$M^p = \begin{pmatrix} & c_1 & c_2 & \dots & c_s \\ A_1 & h_{11}^p & h_{12}^p & \dots & h_{1s}^p \\ A_2 & h_{21}^p & h_{22}^p & & h_{2s}^p \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ A_r & h_{r1}^p & h_{r2}^p & \dots & h_{rs}^p \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Here $p = 1, 2, 3, \dots, t$; $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r$; $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$.

Step: 2. Normalization of the decision matrix

Cost type attributes and benefit type attributes are generally existed in decision making process. Therefore the considered attribute values need to be normalized to avoid different physical dimensional unit. To normalize we can use the following equation:

$$h_{ij}^* = \langle \{1\} - T_{ij}^+, \{1\} - I_{ij}^+, \{1\} - F_{ij}^+, \{-1\} - T_{ij}^-, \{-1\} - I_{ij}^-, \{-1\} - F_{ij}^- \rangle.$$

Using the normalized method, we obtain the following normalized decision matrix (See eq. (5)):

$$M^p = \begin{pmatrix} & c_1 & c_2 & \dots & c_s \\ A_1 & \tilde{h}_{11}^p & \tilde{h}_{12}^p & \dots & \tilde{h}_{1s}^p \\ A_2 & \tilde{h}_{21}^p & \tilde{h}_{22}^p & & \tilde{h}_{2s}^p \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ A_r & \tilde{h}_{r1}^p & \tilde{h}_{r2}^p & \dots & \tilde{h}_{rs}^p \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Where,

$$\tilde{h}_{ij}^p = \begin{cases} h_{ij}^p & \text{if } c_j \text{ is benefit type attribute.} \\ (h_{ij}^*)^p & \text{if } c_j \text{ is cost type attribute.} \end{cases}$$

Step: 3. Aggregation of the decision matrices

Using BNNWA operator in eq. (3), we obtain the aggregated decision matrix as follows:

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} & c_1 & c_2 & \dots & c_s \\ A_1 & h_{11} & h_{12} & \dots & h_{1s} \\ A_2 & h_{21} & h_{22} & & h_{2s} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ A_r & h_{r1} & h_{r2} & \dots & h_{rs} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r$; $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$; $p=1, 2, \dots, t$.

Step: 4. Define the positive ideal solution and negative ideal solution

$$h_{ij}^+ = \langle \max_i T_{ij}^+, \min_i I_{ij}^+, \min_i F_{ij}^+, \min_i T_{ij}^-, \max_i I_{ij}^-, \max_i F_{ij}^- \rangle \quad (7)$$

$$h_{ij}^- = \langle \min_i T_{ij}^+, \max_i I_{ij}^+, \max_i F_{ij}^+, \max_i T_{ij}^-, \min_i I_{ij}^-, \min_i F_{ij}^- \rangle$$

(8)

Step: 5. Define and compute the value of Γ_i and Z_i

($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r$)

Γ_i and Z_i represent the average and worst group scores for the alternative A_i respectively, with the relations

$$\Gamma_i = \sum_{j=1}^s \frac{\alpha_j \times D(h_{ij}^+, \tilde{h}_{ij})}{D(h_{ij}^+, h_{ij}^-)} \quad (9)$$

$$Z_i = \max_j \left\{ \frac{\alpha_j \times D(h_{ij}^+, \tilde{h}_{ij})}{D(h_{ij}^+, h_{ij}^-)} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Here, α_j is the weight of c_j .

The smaller values of Γ_i and Z_i correspond to the better average and worse group scores for alternative A_i , respectively.

Step: 6. Calculate the values of index VIKOR ϕ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r$) by the relation

$$\phi_i = \gamma \frac{(\Gamma_i - \Gamma^-)}{(\Gamma^+ - \Gamma^-)} + (1-\gamma) \frac{(Z_i - Z^-)}{(Z^+ - Z^-)} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Here, } \Gamma_i^- = \min_i \Gamma_i, \Gamma_i^+ = \max_i \Gamma_i, \quad (12)$$

$$Z_i^- = \min_i Z_i, Z_i^+ = \max_i Z_i$$

and γ depicts the decision making mechanism coefficient. If $\gamma > 0.5$, it is for “the maximum group utility”; if $\gamma < 0.5$, it is “the minimum regret”; it has been inferred that the decision making mechanism coefficient is mostly taken as $\gamma = 0.5$.

Step: 7. Rank the priority of alternatives

We rank the alternatives by ϕ_i , Γ_i , and Z_i according to the rule of traditional VIKOR strategy. The smaller value indicates the better alternative.

Figure 1. Decision making procedure of proposed MAGDM strategy.

5. Illustrative example

To demonstrate the applicability and feasibility of the proposed strategy, we solve a MAGDM problem adapted from [45]. We assume that an investment company wants to invest a sum of money in the best option. The investment company forms a decision making board involving of three members (DM_1, DM_2, DM_3) who evaluate the four alternatives to invest money. The alternatives are Car company (A_1), Food company (A_2), Computer company (A_3) and Arm company (A_4). Decision makers take decision to evaluate alternatives based on the criteria namely, risk factor (c_1), growth factor (c_2), environment impact (c_3). We consider three criteria as benefit type based on Zhang et al. [127]. Assume that the weight vector of attributes is

$\alpha=(0.37,0.33,0.3)^T$ and weight vector of decision makers is $\beta=(0.38,0.32,0.3)^T$. Now, we apply the proposed MAGDM strategy to solve the problem using the following steps.

Step: 1. Construction of the decision matrix

We construct the decision matrix information provided by the decision makers in terms of BNNs with respect to the criteria as follows:

$$M^1 = \begin{matrix} & \text{Decision matrix for DM}_1 \\ & \begin{matrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & (.5,.6,.7,-.3,-.6,-.3) & (.8,.5,.6,-.4,-.6,-.3) & (.9,.4,.6,-.1,-.6,-.5) \\ A_2 & (.6,.2,.2,-.4,-.5,-.3) & (.6,.3,.7,-.4,-.3,-.5) & (.7,.5,.3,-.4,-.3,-.3) \\ A_3 & (.8,.3,.5,-.6,-.4,-.5) & (.5,.2,.4,-.1,-.5,-.3) & (.4,.2,.8,-.5,-.3,-.2) \\ A_4 & (.7,.5,.3,-.6,-.3,-.3) & (.8,.7,.2,-.8,-.6,-.1) & (.6,.3,.4,-.3,-.4,-.7) \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

$$M^2 = \begin{matrix} & \text{Decision matrix for DM}_2 \\ & \begin{matrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & (.6,.3,.4,-.5,-.3,-.7) & (.5,.3,.4,-.3,-.3,-.4) & (.1,.5,.7,-.5,-.2,-.6) \\ A_2 & (.7,.4,.5,-.3,-.2,-.1) & (.8,.4,.5,-.7,-.3,-.2) & (.6,.2,.7,-.5,-.2,-.9) \\ A_3 & (.8,.3,.2,-.5,-.2,-.6) & (.3,.2,.1,-.6,-.3,-.4) & (.7,.5,.4,-.4,-.3,-.2) \\ A_4 & (.3,.5,.2,-.5,-.5,-.2) & (.5,.6,.4,-.3,-.6,-.7) & (.4,.3,.8,-.5,-.6,-.5) \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

$$M^3 = \begin{matrix} & \text{Decision matrix for DM}_3 \\ & \begin{matrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & (.9,.6,.4,-.7,-.3,-.2) & (.7,.5,.3,-.6,-.2,-.5) & (.4,.2,.3,-.2,-.5,-.7) \\ A_2 & (.5,.3,.2,-.6,-.4,-.1) & (.5,.2,.7,-.3,-.2,-.5) & (.6,.3,.2,-.7,-.6,-.3) \\ A_3 & (.2,.5,.6,-.4,-.5,-.7) & (.3,.2,.7,-.2,-.3,-.5) & (.8,.2,.4,-.2,-.3,-.6) \\ A_4 & (.8,.5,.5,-.4,-.6,-.3) & (.9,.3,.4,-.5,-.6,-.7) & (.7,.4,.3,-.2,-.5,-.7) \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step: 2. Normalization of the decision matrix

Since all the criteria are considered as benefit type, we do not need to normalize the decision matrices (M^1, M^2, M^3).

Step: 3. Aggregated decision matrix

Using eq. (3), the aggregated decision matrix is presented as follows:

$$M = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & (.22,.17,.17,-.16,-.14,-.13) & (.22,.14,.15,-.14,-.13,-.13) & (.16,.12,.18,-.10,-.10,-.20) \\ A_2 & (.20,.10,.10,-.14,-.12,-.10) & (.21,.10,.21,-.15,-.10,-.13) & (.21,.11,.13,-.17,-.12,-.16) \\ A_3 & (.21,.12,.16,-.17,-.12,-.20) & (.13,.10,.13,-.10,-.12,-.13) & (.21,.10,.18,-.13,-.10,-.11) \\ A_4 & (.20,.17,.11,-.17,-.15,-.10) & (.24,.18,.11,-.19,-.20,-.16) & (.19,.11,.17,-.11,-.16,-.21) \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step: 4. Define the positive ideal solution and negative ideal solution

The positive ideal solution $h_{ij}^+ =$

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \\ (.22,.10,.10,-.14,-.12,-.10) & (.24,.10,.11,-.19,-.10,-.13) & (.21,.10,.13,-.17,-.10,-.11) \end{pmatrix}$$

 and the negative ideal solution

$h_{ij}^- =$

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \\ (.20,.17,.17,-.14,-.15,-.20) & (.13,.18,.21,-.10,-.20,-.16) & (.16,.12,.18,-.10,-.16,-.11) \end{pmatrix}$$

Step: 5. Compute Γ_i and Z_i

We have computed the values of Γ_i by eq. (9) and the values of Z_i by eq. (10), the values are presented as follows:

$\Gamma_1 = 0.75, \Gamma_2 = 0.38, \Gamma_3 = 0.60, \Gamma_4 = 0.75$ and $Z_1 = 0.34, Z_2 = 0.16, Z_3 = 0.33, Z_4 = 0.34$

Step: 6. Calculate the values of ϕ_i

Using $\gamma=0.5$, and eq. (11) and eq. (12), we obtain $\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.77, \phi_4 = 1$

Step: 7. Rank the priority of alternatives

The preference order of the alternatives based on the traditional rules of the VIKOR strategy is $A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 \approx A_1$.

6. The influence of parameter γ

In this section, we present sensitivity analysis to show the impact of different values of the decision making mechanism coefficient on ranking order of the alternatives Figure 2 represents the graphical representation of alternatives (A_i) versus ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) for different values of γ .

Table 1 shows that the ranking order of alternatives (A_i) with the value of γ changing from 0.1 to 0.9.

Values of γ	Values of ϕ_i	Preference order of alternatives
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$\gamma = 0.1$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.915, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.2$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.880, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.3$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.845, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.4$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.810, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.5$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.770, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.6$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.740, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.7$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.700, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.8$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.670, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$
$\gamma = 0.9$	$\phi_1 = 1, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = 0.640, \phi_4 = 1$	$A_2 \succ A_3 \succ A_4 = A_1$

Table 1. Values of ϕ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) and ranking of alternatives for different values of γ .

Fig 2. Graphical representation of ranking order of alternatives for different values of γ .

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we have extended the VIKOR strategy to MAGDM with bipolar neutrosophic environment. We have introduced bipolar neutrosophic numbers weighted aggregation operator and applied it to aggregate the individual opinion to one group opinion. We have developed a VIKOR based MAGDM strategy with bipolar neutrosophic set. Finally, we have solved a MAGDM problem to show the feasibility and efficiency of the proposed MAGDM strategy. We have presented a sensitivity analysis to show the impact of different values of the decision making mechanism coefficient on ranking order of the alternatives. The proposed VIKOR based MAGDM strategy can be employed to solve a variety of problems such as logistics center selection [128], teacher selection [19, 129], renewable energy selection [131], fault diagnosis [132], weaver selection [14, 54], brick selection [13], school choice [130] etc.

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